

1 NLR receptors in plant immunity: making sense of the alphabet soup

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6 7 **Abstract:**

8
9 Plants co-ordinately use cell-surface and intracellular immune receptors to perceive pathogens and
10 mount an immune response. Intracellular events of pathogen recognition are largely mediated by
11 immune receptors of the nucleotide binding and leucine rich-repeat (NLR) class. Upon pathogen
12 perception, NLRs trigger a potent broad-spectrum immune reaction usually accompanied by a
13 form of programmed cell death termed the hypersensitive response. Some plant NLRs act as
14 multifunctional singleton receptors which combine pathogen detection and immune signaling.
15 However, NLRs can also function in higher order pairs and networks of functionally specialized
16 interconnected receptors. In this article we cover the basic aspects of plant NLR biology with an
17 emphasis on NLR networks. We highlight some of the recent advances in NLR structure, function
18 and activation and discuss emerging topics such as modulator NLRs, pathogen suppression of
19 NLRs and NLR bioengineering. Multi-disciplinary approaches are required to disentangle how
20 these NLR immune receptor pairs and networks function and evolve. Answering these questions
21 holds the potential to deepen our understanding of the plant immune system and unlock a new
22 era of disease resistance breeding.

23 24 **Keywords:**

25
26 NB-LRR, NOD, NBS-LRR, immunology, bioengineering

27 28 **Introduction:**

29
30 Plants have a sophisticated multi-layered innate immune system which actively protects them
31 against pathogen invasion (Jones *et al*, 2016; Ngou *et al*, 2022a). They co-ordinately use cell-surface
32 and intracellular immune receptors to perceive pathogens and mount an immune response. To
33 successfully infect their host, pathogens secrete virulence proteins, termed effectors. Effectors
34 typically promote disease by modulating host physiology and by suppressing cell-surface or

35 intracellular immunity (Couto & Zipfel, 2016; Wu & Derevnina, 2023). Some of these effectors
36 are recognized by the protein products of plant *resistance* (*R*) genes, which largely belong to the
37 nucleotide binding and leucine rich-repeat (NLR) class (Kourelis & Van Der Hoorn, 2018).
38 Effector recognition by NLRs leads to effector-triggered immunity (ETI), also known as NLR-
39 triggered immunity. ETI is a robust immune response usually accompanied by a form of
40 programmed cell death, known as the hypersensitive response or hypersensitive cell death (Jones
41 & Dangl, 2006; Ngou *et al.*, 2022a).

42

43 In the 1950s, Harold Flor first proposed a framework for host-pathogen interactions termed the
44 gene-for-gene model, in which matching pairs of genes from a host and a pathogen determine the
45 outcome of a given interaction (Flor, 1971). Many NLR-effector pairs follow this model, where
46 the presence of a single pathogen gene, termed avirulence (AVR) gene, triggers immunity in hosts
47 carrying a single matching NLR gene (Jones & Dangl, 2006). These AVR genes usually encode
48 effector proteins. As such, plant parasites are under constant pressure from their hosts to diversify
49 their effector gene repertoire to evade recognition while maintaining virulence. On the other hand,
50 plants and their NLRs constantly evolve their resistance gene repertoire to keep up with rapidly
51 evolving pathogens. This has resulted in tremendous genetic innovation, with NLR-coding genes
52 being the most diverse genes in plants (Baggs *et al.*, 2017; Barragan & Weigel, 2021; Clark *et al.*,
53 2007). Over time, this evolutionary arms race has likely contributed to an increase in NLR
54 complexity, with NLRs becoming sub-functionalized and evolving from single individual genetic
55 units, or “singletons” to higher order configurations, such as NLR pairs or networks.

56

57 In NLR pairs and networks, multiple immune receptors work together to achieve robust immunity.
58 Sensor NLRs mediate pathogen perception and activate downstream helper NLRs which mediate
59 immune signaling. Unlike NLR pairs, which function in one-to-one sensor-helper connections,
60 NLR networks simultaneously exhibit many-to-one and one-to-many functional sensor-helper
61 connections, likely contributing to increased robustness and evolvability of the plant immune
62 system (**Figure 1**) (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Feehan *et al.*, 2020; Wu *et al.*, 2017; Wu *et al.*, 2018).

63

64 In this review, we aim to cover the basic aspects of plant NLR biology, with an emphasis on NLR
65 network biology. We touch on recent breakthroughs in NLR structure, function, and activation,
66 which have provided insights into how NLRs translate pathogen perception into immune signaling
67 via oligomerization-based mechanisms. Moreover, we discuss emerging areas of study in plant
68 NLR biology such as modulator NLRs, pathogen suppression of NLRs and NLR bioengineering.

69 Overall, we highlight the wide structural and functional diversity of NLR mediated immunity along
70 with the higher order of complexity presented by NLR pairs and networks.

71

72 **What is an NLR?**

73

74 NLR proteins are found across all kingdoms of life and exhibit a conserved tripartite modular
75 domain architecture (Duxbury *et al*, 2021; Gao *et al*, 2022; Kibby *et al*, 2023; Uehling *et al*, 2017). In
76 their broadest definition, they are STAND (signal transduction ATPases with numerous domains)
77 proteins comprised of an N-terminal domain, a central nucleotide-binding and oligomerization
78 domain (NOD) and C-terminal superstructure-forming repeats (SSFRs) (Dyrka *et al*, 2020;
79 Kourelis *et al*, 2021). N-terminal domains are usually thought of as signaling domains, and in plant
80 NLRs they often mediate the downstream programmed cell death response, following immune
81 receptor activation (Duxbury *et al*, 2021). The plant NLR NOD is exclusively an NB-ARC
82 (nucleotide-binding adaptor shared by APAF-1, certain R gene products, and CED-4) domain,
83 whereas the C-terminal SSFRs are typically leucine rich repeat (LRR) domains (Kourelis *et al*,
84 2021).

85

86 Plant NLRs, like most STAND proteins, are molecular switches (Takken *et al*, 2006). They exist in
87 an inactive ADP-bound resting state and conditionally initiate immune signaling upon perception
88 of non-self or modified-self (Gao *et al*, 2022; Jones *et al*, 2016; Takken & Goverse, 2012). The
89 central NB-ARC domain is critical for mediating conformational changes required for switching
90 between inactive to active states, primarily through the exchange of ADP for ATP at its nucleotide
91 binding pocket (Takken *et al*, 2006; Wang *et al*, 2019b). While the C-terminal LRR can, in some
92 cases, determine pathogen perception, this domain also mediates critical autoinhibitory intra-
93 molecular interactions that hold the receptor in an inactive state prior to activation (Förderer *et al*,
94 2022; Takken & Goverse, 2012). Following activation and release of intramolecular auto-
95 inhibition, the N-terminal domains can subsequently mediate downstream immune signaling.

96

97 Plant NLRs exhibit diverse N-terminal signaling domains, which can be used to broadly classify
98 them into distinct classes. These classes follow the phylogeny of the NB-ARC domain indicating
99 that they have a deep evolutionary origin (Kourelis *et al*, 2021). To date, four main N-terminal
100 signaling domains have been characterized in angiosperms: Coiled-coil (CC)-type, RESISTANCE
101 TO POWDERY MILDEW 8 (RPW8)-type (CC_R), G10-type CC (CC_{G10}) and toll/interleukin-1
102 receptor-type (TIR) (Kourelis *et al*, 2021). NLRs in non-flowering plants can carry additional types

103 of N-terminal domains, such as a/b hydrolases and kinase domains (Andolfo *et al*, 2019; Chia *et al*,
104 2022). In general, the N-terminal domain is thought to dictate the type of downstream signaling
105 pathways and activities that take place following NLR activation.

106

107 Although the majority of plant NLRs retain the canonical and presumably ancestral tri-partite
108 domain organization, many NLRs have diversified into specialized proteins with additional non-
109 canonical domains or degenerated features (Adachi *et al*, 2019a; Cesari *et al*, 2014; Kourelis *et al*,
110 2021). As we uncover more NLR structural and functional diversity, it is imperative that we revise
111 the way in which we conceptualize NLR domains and their roles in immune receptor activities.

112

113 **NLRs are highly expanded and diverse in plants**

114

115 In addition to their role in plant defence, NLRs have also been the subject of extensive
116 investigation in the field of evolutionary biology, as they have undergone rapid evolution and
117 diversification in response to strong selection pressures from rapidly evolving pathogens. Large-
118 scale comparative phylogenomic analyses have revealed that NLR-encoding genes are some of the
119 most diverse and quickly evolving in plant genomes (Barragan & Weigel, 2021; Clark *et al*, 2007;
120 Prigozhin & Krasileva, 2021). They occur in all major groups of flowering plants (angiosperms)
121 and non-flowering plants, with some NLR-like genes being found in green algae (Andolfo *et al*,
122 2019; Chia *et al*, 2022; Shao *et al*, 2019). This phylogenetically informed view of NLRs revealed
123 that they are diverse in many ways. The number of NLRs varies greatly across species, ranging
124 from ~50 in watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) and papaya (*Carica papaya*) to >1000 in apple (*Malus*
125 *domestica*) and hexaploid wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) (Baggs *et al*, 2017; Jia *et al*, 2015; Steuernagel *et al*,
126 2020). NLRs exhibit lineage-specific expansions and contractions, which usually occur through
127 tandem duplication and/or deletion events in each species, often influenced by transposon
128 content, ecological context and adaptation to their environment (Baggs *et al*, 2017; Barragan &
129 Weigel, 2021). NLR genes also exhibit tremendous intraspecific diversity, exhibiting
130 presence/absence variation and heterogeneity in allelic variation, largely due to point mutations,
131 intra-allelic recombination and domain fusions or swaps (Lin *et al*, 2022; MacQueen *et al*, 2019;
132 Maekawa *et al*, 2019; Prigozhin & Krasileva, 2021; Seeholzer *et al*, 2010; Seong *et al*, 2020; Shimizu
133 *et al*, 2022; Van de Weyer *et al*, 2019).

134

135 The recently generated RefPlantNLR collection of almost 500 experimentally validated NLRs
136 nicely illustrates our current grasp of NLR diversity in terms of domain architecture and function,

137 showcasing that plants have evolved NLRs to detect effectors from most plant pathogenic
138 organisms (Kourelis *et al.*, 2021). Importantly, looking at the plant species represented in the
139 RefPlantNLR dataset highlighted that most NLRs characterized to date come from a relatively
140 small pool of flowering plant species. Our understanding of broader NLR domain structure and
141 molecular function, in particular outside of crop and model plant species or in nonflowering plants,
142 is therefore limited. Only recently, a study by Chia *et al.* (2022) functionally characterized NLRs
143 and NLR signaling domains from deep lineages of land plants and algae, revealing that there are
144 indeed shared NLR activities spanning the whole spectrum of plant evolution. Notably, this study
145 leveraged transient heterologous expression in the model flowering plant *Nicotiana benthamiana* as
146 a powerful tool to perform functional screens of N-terminal CC, CC_R and TIR-type signaling
147 domains from divergent algal and plant genomes. They found that many of these retained the
148 capacity to trigger hypersensitive cell death like their angiosperm counterparts. This indicates that
149 some NLR signaling domains and their functions arose early during plant evolution and have
150 retained these functions over long evolutionary time (Chia *et al.*, 2022). Nonetheless, much NLR
151 functional diversity in underrepresented or understudied plant species remains to be explored.
152 This study is a perfect example of how powerful these comparative approaches can be to identify
153 important commonalities and differences in NLR function. Integrating phylogenetics,
154 evolutionary biology and functional studies into NLR research is critical to uncover the full
155 potential of these diverse plant proteins.

156

157 **NLR receptors are intracellular sensors of invading pathogens**

158

159 Plant NLRs sense intracellular effectors delivered by pathogens during infection and subsequently
160 trigger an immune response (Jones & Dangl, 2006; Lolle *et al.*, 2020). The strategies by which NLRs
161 recognize effectors can generally be divided into two categories: direct and indirect recognition.
162 Direct recognition of effectors follows a receptor-ligand model, with one NLR protein binding
163 one effector molecule (Baggs *et al.*, 2017). For example, the wheat CC-NLR Sr35 directly binds the
164 effector AvrSr35 via its LRR domain. Effector binding relieves intramolecular autoinhibition in
165 Sr35 and triggers conformational rearrangements which lead to Sr35 activation (Förderer *et al.*,
166 2022; Zhao *et al.*, 2022). The TIR-NLRs RPP1 from *Arabidopsis* and Roq1 from *N. benthamiana* also
167 recognise their cognate effectors via direct binding. RPP1 recognises the effector ATR1 from the
168 oomycete *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis*, while Roq1 recognizes the *Xanthomonas perforans* effector
169 XopQ. In both cases, effector binding occurs in the LRR, assisted by a post-LRR region found in
170 some TIR-NLRs, known as the C-terminal jelly roll and Ig-like domain (C-JID). Effector binding

171 by RPP1 and Roq1 also induces conformational rearrangements leading to NLR activation and
172 downstream signaling (Ma *et al*, 2020; Martin *et al*, 2020).

173

174 Sr35, RPP1 and Roq1 are well studied cases in which cryogenic electron microscopy (Cryo-EM)
175 structures of NLRs in complex with their cognate effectors have resolved the ligand binding
176 interfaces with intricate detail, but many additional examples of NLRs that directly recognize
177 effectors exist (Bauer *et al*, 2021; Catanzariti *et al*, 2010; Chen *et al*, 2017; Dodds *et al*, 2006; Jia *et al*,
178 2000; Zhu *et al*, 2017). In most of these examples, the LRR domain plays a critical role in
179 determining effector recognition specificity. For the tomato CC-NLR Sw5-b, which directly
180 recognizes the NSm viral protein of different tospoviruses (Peiró *et al*, 2014; Zhu *et al*, 2017), the
181 LRR also plays a key role in effector binding, although an additional domain located before the N-
182 terminal CC domain, known as the Solanaceous domain (SD) also contributes to direct interaction
183 with the effector (Zhu *et al*, 2017).

184

185 While direct recognition of effectors by NLRs would seem like the most intuitive and simple
186 strategy to perceive pathogens, there are comparatively more examples in which effectors are
187 indirectly recognized. Some NLRs can monitor or “guard” host components targeted by pathogen
188 effectors, which are therefore termed “guardees” (Jones & Dangl, 2006). The CC-NLR Prf from
189 tomato guards the host kinase Pto by sensing its interaction with the bacterial effectors AvrPto
190 and AvrPtoB to trigger Prf-dependent immune signaling (Kim *et al*, 2002). The Resistance to
191 *Pseudomonas syringae* 5 (RPS5) CC_{G10}-NLR from *Arabidopsis* guards the host kinase PBS1.
192 Cleavage of PBS1 by the bacterial protease AvrPphB leads to RPS5-mediated immunity (Ade *et al*,
193 2007). In their attempts to manipulate host physiology and immunity, different effectors either
194 from the same, or from phylogenetically unrelated pathogens, sometimes converge on the same
195 host proteins to promote disease (Derevnina *et al*, 2021; Macho & Zipfel, 2015; Mukhtar *et al*,
196 2011; Petre *et al*, 2021; Song *et al*, 2009). One example is the recognition of the *P. syringae* effectors
197 AvrRpm1, AvrB and AvrRpt2. These three effectors modify the host protein RIN4,
198 phosphorylating it in the case of AvrRpm1 and AvrB or cleaving it in the case of AvrRpt2. In turn,
199 the CC-NLR RESISTANCE TO *P. SYRINGAE* PV MACULICOLA 1 (RPM1) and the CC_{G10}-
200 NLR RESISTANCE TO *P. SYRINGAE* 2 (RPS2) guard RIN4, sensing its phosphorylation or
201 cleavage, respectively, leading to immunity (Axtell & Staskawicz, 2003; Mackey *et al*, 2003).

202

203 A derivation of the guard-guardee model is the decoy model. Whereas some NLR guardees are
204 functional host proteins with discernible physiological roles, decoys are host proteins which

205 evolved to bait pathogen effectors, without other clear functions in host physiology (van der
206 Hoorn & Kamoun, 2008). For example, ZAR1 can recognize a range of bacterial effectors through
207 its partner receptor-like cytoplasmic kinases (RLCKs), also termed ZED1-related kinases (ZRKs)
208 (**Figure 1**) (Adachi *et al*, 2023b; Laflamme *et al*, 2020; Schultink *et al*, 2019; Seto *et al*, 2017; Wang
209 *et al*, 2015). ZED1 and RKS1 are two such RLCKs which constitutively form a complex with
210 ZAR1. The *Xanthomonas campestris pv. campestris* effector HopZ1a acetylates ZED1, and this
211 modification is sensed by ZAR1, triggering its activation. The effector AvrAC from *P. syringae*
212 uridylylates the RLCK PBL2. This modified PBL2 then conditionally interacts with the pre-formed
213 ZAR1-RKS1 complex, triggering an immune response. Because ZED1 is a pseudokinase and
214 PBL2 uridylylation does not enhance AvrAC-mediated virulence, these host proteins are
215 considered decoys dedicated to baiting pathogen effectors (Lewis *et al*, 2013; Wang *et al*, 2015).

216

217 How does indirect recognition aid in keeping up with rapidly evolving pathogen effectors? Indirect
218 effector recognition allows plants to maximize the efficacy of a fixed number of immune receptors.
219 NLRs that indirectly recognize pathogens by guarding common virulence targets are more versatile
220 than direct effector binders, as they hold the potential to recognize multiple effectors
221 simultaneously, even if these effectors are unrelated in structure or sequence or are secreted by
222 different pathogens and pests. From an evolutionary point of view, guarding of pathways that are
223 commonly targeted by multiple pathogens enable plants to have a wider surveillance mechanism
224 than responding to specific pathogen molecules. Moreover, guardees/decoys that are dedicated to
225 effector sensing should be less evolutionarily constrained than NLRs that execute the immune
226 response. This model has analogies to the NLR sensor/helper pairing discussed below, except that
227 the sensing activity is performed by a non-NLR moiety. Along these lines, guardees/decoys can
228 potentially accumulate a higher number of mutations because they do not retain the original
229 functionality of their progenitor protein, allowing them to better keep up with rapidly evolving
230 effectors (**Figure 1**).

231

232 **Figure 1: Evolution of NLR singletons, pairs, and networks.**

233

234 (A) The NLR ZAR1 indirectly recognises multiple bacterial effectors by guarding host RLCKs, also termed
 235 ZRKs, which bait bacterial effectors. Over evolutionary time, ZRKs have greatly diversified as a result of
 236 coevolution with pathogen effectors. In contrast, ZAR1 has remained atypically conserved throughout
 237 angiosperm evolution, relying on ZRKs for pathogen recognition and specializing in interacting with ZRKs
 238 to mediate immune signaling. (B) NLRs can be categorized into functional singletons, pairs, and networks.
 239 While singletons can mediate both, pathogen sensing and downstream immune signaling, NLRs have
 240 duplicated and diversified over evolutionary time leading to the appearance of specialized receptors that
 241 can be defines as either ‘sensors’ or ‘helpers’, forming connections that range from pairs to complex
 242 networks.

243

244 **NLR-IDs: NLRs with unconventional integrated domains**

245

246 Moving beyond the canonical tri-partite domain architecture, up to 10% of the NLRome of a
 247 given plant species can consist of NLRs with additional insertions known as integrated domains
 248 (IDs). These IDs often mimic the host targets of effectors (Cesari *et al.*, 2014; Kroj *et al.*, 2016;
 249 Sarris *et al.*, 2016). Within the NLR, IDs can be involved in effector sensing, either via direct or

250 indirect recognition (De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2018; Fujisaki *et al.*, 2015; Gu *et al.*, 2023; Maqbool *et*
251 *al.*, 2015). The integrated decoy hypothesis postulates that over evolutionary time, host targets of
252 effectors have genetically integrated within NLRs, baiting pathogen effectors to activate host
253 immunity (Cesari *et al.*, 2014). The well characterized rice CC-NLRs Pik-1 and RGA5 (aka Pia-2)
254 feature an integrated domain known as Heavy Metal Associated (HMA) which binds multiple
255 effectors from the rice blast fungus, *Magnaporthe oryzae*, to mediate disease resistance. These NLRs
256 can directly recognize multiple *M. oryzae* effectors: Pik-1 recognizes AVR-Pik and AVR-Mgk1,
257 while RGA5 recognizes AVR1-CO39 and AVR-Pia (Cesari *et al.*, 2013; De la Concepcion *et al.*,
258 2018; Guo *et al.*, 2018; Maqbool *et al.*, 2015; Sugihara *et al.*, 2023).

259

260 Identification of the host targets of effectors recognized by NLR-IDs supported the hypothesis
261 that IDs are derived from host target integration. For both, Pik-1 and RGA5, the cognate effectors
262 are sequence unrelated but share a conserved structural fold, termed the MAX fold (Magnaporthe
263 AVRs and ToxB-like) (de Guillen *et al.*, 2015). MAX fold effectors have been shown to bind
264 endogenous "non-integrated" HMA proteins from the host, supporting the notion that over
265 evolutionary time HMAs have integrated into NLRs to mimic the host targets of MAX effectors
266 (Bentham *et al.*, 2021; Bialas *et al.*, 2021; Maidment *et al.*, 2021; Oikawa *et al.*, 2020). Another well-
267 studied example is the RRS1 TIR-NLR from *Arabidopsis* which features a C-terminal integrated
268 WRKY transcription factor-like domain. The bacterial effectors AvrRps4 from *P. syringae* and
269 PopP2 from *Ralstonia solanacearum* can modify host WRKY transcription factors to promote disease
270 (Le Roux *et al.*, 2015; Pandey & Somssich, 2009; Sarris *et al.*, 2015). The C-terminal integrated
271 WRKY domain of RRS1 acts as a bait for these effectors, as RRS1 can sense its modification to
272 activate immunity (Le Roux *et al.*, 2015; Mukhi *et al.*, 2021). Interestingly, all functionally
273 characterized NLR-IDs to date require a second, genetically linked, NLR to confer disease
274 resistance and are therefore known as a "paired" NLRs (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Cesari *et al.*, 2014)

275

276 A diversity of domains have fused to NLRs over evolutionary time, suggesting that there is a
277 degree of flexibility in terms of what domains can potentially be integrated into NLR-IDs (Marchal
278 *et al.*, 2022a; Sarris *et al.*, 2016). A striking case is the Pia/Pias allelic/ortholog series from the *Oryza*
279 genus. In this example, variants of the same NLR exhibit at least 9 different integrations, including
280 HMA domains, protein-kinase domains or WRKY domains (Shimizu *et al.*, 2022). While recent
281 works have shed light on how IDs evolve following integration, and how intramolecular ID-NLR
282 scaffold interactions shape NLR-ID function (Bialas *et al.*, 2021; De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2021),
283 how NLRs evolve to generate novel domains is not fully understood (**Box 1**). Understanding NLR-

284 ID evolution can inform NLR bioengineering strategies, as discussed in the corresponding section
285 of this review.

286

287 **NLR singletons and pairs**

288

289 Some NLRs function as individual genetic units and are therefore termed functional singleton
290 NLRs. These can directly or indirectly perceive pathogen effectors and induce a downstream
291 immune response without relying on additional NLRs (**Figure 1**) (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a). Well
292 studied immune receptors in this category include the CC-NLRs ZAR1 from *Arabidopsis* and
293 Sr35 from wheat. As mentioned previously, ZAR1 indirectly recognizes its cognate effectors via
294 its guard/decoy RLCKs, while Sr35 binds AvrSr35 directly via its LRR (Förderer *et al.*, 2022;
295 Wang *et al.*, 2019a; Zhao *et al.*, 2022). Other NLRs that are considered likely singletons based on
296 their capacity to sense effectors and trigger hypersensitive cell death in heterologous plant systems
297 include Sr50, several NLRs in the MLA allelic series, RPS5 and RPP13 (Chen *et al.*, 2017; Maekawa
298 *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2012; Ravensdale *et al.*, 2012; Saur *et al.*, 2019). To this end, *Agrobacterium*
299 *tumefaciens*-mediated transient expression (aka agroinfiltration) of NLR proteins in leaves of *N.*
300 *benthamiana* has been a useful method for heterologous expression of immune receptors. If an CC-
301 NLR from an unrelated species is capable of triggering cell death in *N. benthamiana*, it likely
302 functions as a singleton or helper. Although this test is not definitive and depends on the degree
303 of conservation of potential downstream signaling partners, decoys or guardees, it serves as a first
304 approach to classify NLRs into functional categories and further exemplifies how *N. benthamiana*
305 can be an excellent system to quickly functionally characterize and categorize NLRs (Adachi *et al.*,
306 2019b; Derevnina *et al.*, 2019).

307

308 In paired NLR systems, one immune receptor is specialized in pathogen perception acting as a
309 sensor and requires a downstream helper NLR to induce immune signaling. Some well-studied
310 “model” paired NLR systems include the rice Pik-1/Pik-2 and RGA5/RGA4 (Pia) CC-NLR pairs
311 and the *Arabidopsis* RRS1/RPS4 TIR-NLR pair. The genes coding for the Pik-1 NLR-ID and its
312 helper NLR Pik-2 are found in head-to-head orientation and are both required for resistance to
313 the blast fungus *M. oryzae* (**Figure 1, Figure 2**). Pik-1 binding to *M. oryzae* effectors leads to
314 activation of immunity via its helper Pik-2, with both NLRs working cooperatively to mediate
315 disease resistance. Pik-1 is unable to trigger cell death in the absence of its downstream helper Pik-
316 2 (De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2021; Maqbool *et al.*, 2015; Zdrzałek *et al.*, 2020). In the case of RGA5
317 and its helper RGA4, these NLRs work by negative regulation rather than by cooperation (Césari

318 *et al.*, 2014). The RGA4 helper has been shown to be constitutively active, triggering cell death
319 when heterologously expressed in *N. benthamiana* (Césari *et al.*, 2014). Co-expression of its sensor
320 NLR-ID mate RGA5 can suppress this constitutive activity. Upon effector binding by RGA5, this
321 negative regulation is relieved enabling RGA4 to mediate immune signaling (Césari *et al.*, 2014).

322

323 The genetically linked Arabidopsis TIR-NLR pair RRS1/RPS4 similarly works via negative
324 regulation. RPS4 is constitutively active in *Arabidopsis*, triggering immune signaling in the absence
325 of pathogen infection if the RRS1 sensor, which acts as its repressor, is not present. RRS1
326 inhibition of RPS4 is conditionally relieved upon effector perception. While RRS1 and RPS4 are
327 genetically linked paired NLRs, they require a genetically unlinked downstream helper CC_R-NLR,
328 NRG1, to confer disease resistance (**Figure 1, Figure 3**). Therefore, whether RPS4 should be
329 termed a helper for RRS1 is up for debate, as the term helper is often associated with a CC or
330 CC_R-type NLR acting downstream of a sensor (Gong *et al.*, 2023). These, as well as additional
331 examples of paired NLR systems have been extensively reviewed (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Feehan *et*
332 *al.*, 2020; Gong *et al.*, 2023; Marchal *et al.*, 2022a; Xi *et al.*, 2022).

333

334 **NLR networks: the emergence of complex NLR systems**

335

336 In some cases, NLRs have evolved more complex connections beyond paired sensor-helper
337 configurations. Cases in which more than two NLRs are connected functionally are referred to as
338 NLR networks (Adachi & Kamoun, 2022; Duxbury *et al.*, 2021; Kourelis & Adachi, 2022; Wu *et*
339 *al.*, 2017; Wu *et al.*, 2018). Networked NLRs can be genetically unlinked yet phylogenetically related
340 and exhibit a sensor and helper dynamic (**Figure 1, Figure 2**). Unlike paired NLRs which exhibit
341 one-to-one connections, NLR network components can exhibit “one-to-many” and “many-to-
342 one” signaling architectures. Different sensors can converge on one downstream helper and each
343 individual sensor can signal redundantly via more than one helper (Wu *et al.*, 2017; Wu *et al.*, 2018).
344 Helpers themselves are not necessarily fully redundant, and can exhibit a degree of functional
345 specialization, both in terms of compatibility with upstream sensors and of downstream signaling
346 (Saile *et al.*, 2020; Wu *et al.*, 2017). NLR networks combine the higher degree of receptor evolvability
347 conferred by sensor-helper specialization, as seen in paired NLR systems, with the robustness
348 conferred by genetic redundancy at the helper level (**Figure 1**) (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Castel *et al.*,
349 2019; Gong *et al.*, 2023; Wu *et al.*, 2017).

350

351 In Solanaceous plants, helper NLRs known as NRCs (NLR Required for Cell death) are genetically
352 required for immune signalling by a multitude of sensor NLRs and cell-surface receptors that
353 mediate perception of diverse plant pathogenic oomycetes, fungi, nematodes, insects, viruses, and
354 bacteria (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Kourelis *et al.*, 2022; Oh *et al.*, 2023; Wu *et al.*, 2017). In *Nicotiana*
355 *benthamiana*, the CC-NLRs NRC2, NRC3 and NRC4 act as key nodes in this network (Wu *et al.*,
356 2017). Another well characterized example is the NRG1/ADR1 network, in which the CC_R-NLRs
357 NRG1 and ADR1 act as helpers, inducing immune signaling and cell death downstream of
358 multiple sensor TIR-type NLRs (TIR-NLRs) (Bonardi *et al.*, 2011; Castel *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2018;
359 Wu *et al.*, 2019). In this case, the TIR-NLRs play essentially the role of sensor NLRs although more
360 complex network functionalities probably take place.

361

362 The prevalence of NLR pairs and networks in plants indicates the limits of the conceptual
363 framework of NLR domains and their functions, which describes the canonical NLR functions in
364 the context of a functional singleton. For example, in the case of helper NLRs which do not engage
365 in effector recognition, the LRR may have adopted new activities, such as in mediating sensor-
366 helper communication.

367 **Asymmetrical evolution of paired and networked NLRs**

368

369 In some cases, notably the NRC helpers and their sensors, CC-NLR pairs and networks have been
370 proposed to originate from multifunctional “singleton” ancestors that have biochemically sub-
371 functionalized over evolutionary time (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Wu *et al.*, 2018) (**Figure 1**). This
372 division of labour presumably facilitates keeping up with rapidly evolving pathogen effectors, as it
373 results in reduced evolutionary constraints for both the sensor and helper, thus enhancing
374 evolvability of the network components and the system as a whole. By specializing, NLR pairs
375 broaden the potential spectrum of amino acid changes and domain integrations that can be
376 accommodated in each of the immune receptor, since individual sensor and helper proteins no
377 longer need to fulfil both functions (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a). The acquisition of new domains for
378 pathogen detection in sensor NLRs is likely facilitated by this functional specialization. For
379 example, the majority of characterized NLR-IDs to date are paired with helper NLRs (Marchal *et al.*,
380 2022a). In the Pik and Pia paired NLR allelic series, higher levels of variation are found in the
381 sensor NLR, specifically within the effector-sensing ID (Bialas *et al.*, 2021; De la Concepcion *et al.*,
382 2021; Shimizu *et al.*, 2022). In the NRC network, many NRC-dependent sensor NLRs include N-
383 terminal Solanaceae Domain (SD), which can participate in pathogen perception (Li *et al.*, 2019;
384 Lukasik-Shreepaathy *et al.*, 2012; Mucyn *et al.*, 2006). That NLRs with additional pathogen sensing

385 domains such as IDs or SDs are found in paired or networked configurations therefore highlights
386 the enhanced evolvability granted by sensor-helper NLR specialization (**Figure 1, Figure 3**)
387 (Marchal *et al.*, 2022a; Wu *et al.*, 2017). It is also conceivable that the evolutionary steps leading to
388 incorporation of additional domains would be less likely to lead to autoimmunity in a functionally
389 specialized sensor NLR than in a singleton.

390

391 Paired or networked signaling configurations can also lead to regressive evolution of NLR
392 proteins. The MADA motif found in the N-terminal α 1-helices of around 20% of all angiosperm
393 CC-NLRs is crucial for cell death initiation. MADA and MADA-like motifs, such as the MAEPL
394 motif of non-flowering plants, are present and functionally conserved in evolutionarily distant
395 NLRs that can execute cell death. Examples of NLRs with an N-terminal MADA motif include
396 singleton NLRs such as the atypically ancient NLR ZAR1, helper NLRs such as Pik-2 and NRC4
397 and several *M. polymorpha* CC-NLRs, indicating that these CC-NLRs share a common origin and
398 that the MADA-type α 1-helix traces back to the origin of land plants (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Adachi
399 *et al.*, 2023b; Chia *et al.*, 2022). In contrast, sensor NLR specialization towards pathogen perception
400 is often accompanied by loss or degeneration of the MADA motif making these protein incapable
401 of activating immunity on their own (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a).

402

403 In the Pik-1/Pik-2 NLR pair, the Pik-2 helper carries an N-terminal MADA motif, whereas the
404 Pik-1 sensor does not (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a). Pik-1 features an integrated HMA domain through
405 which it interacts with pathogen effectors and is unable to trigger cell death in the absence of Pik-
406 2 (De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2021; Kanzaki *et al.*, 2012; Zdrzalek *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, while the
407 NRC helpers contain a MADA motif, none of the NRC-dependent sensors carry a detectable
408 MADA sequence (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Chia *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, the N-termini of MADA or
409 MAEPL motif containing NLRs can functionally substitute the N-terminus of the helper NRC4
410 whereas the N-termini of sensor CC-NLRs cannot (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Chia *et al.*, 2022). This
411 evolutionary “use-it-or-lose-it” model postulates that conserved motifs in the N-termini of sensor
412 NLRs became degenerated into “non-functional” sequences as a consequence of relying on
413 helpers for cell death induction (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Adachi *et al.*, 2019b).

414

415 **Phylogenomics of NLR pairs and networks: making sense of the alphabet soup**

416

417 The genomic location of NLR genes across plant species has revealed clues about their
418 evolutionary history. NLRs can be encoded in genetic clusters or dispersed as genetic singletons.

419 In Arabidopsis, around 50% of all NLRs are found in clustered arrangements which arose by
420 tandem gene duplication or unequal crossing-over events (Lee & Chae, 2020; Van de Weyer *et al.*,
421 2019). NLRs that are dispersed throughout the genome often lack introns and were proposed to
422 have expanded through retroduplication events (Kim *et al.*, 2017). These gene duplication events
423 enable NLRs to sub-functionalize, acquire new activities and domains and functionally diverge,
424 leading to a variety of gene clusters that consist of either a series of phylogenetically related genes
425 or NLR genes of mixed origin (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b).

426

427 NLR sensor-helper pairs, such as rice Pik-1/Pik-2 or Pia (aka RGA5/RGA4), are usually
428 genetically clustered in tight physical linkage, sometimes in head-to-head orientation (Bialas *et al.*,
429 2021; Césari *et al.*, 2014; Stein *et al.*, 2018) (**Figure 2**). This presumably allows for transcriptional
430 co-regulation of sensors and helpers genes. The Pik-1 and Pik-2 pair, for example, are transcribed
431 from a shared promoter (Ashikawa *et al.*, 2008; De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2018). This physical linkage
432 also facilitates co-segregation of functionally connected sensor and helper pairs. This is important
433 considering that some helpers are constitutively active as discussed above, and inheritance of the
434 helper without the sensor would have deleterious effects on the plant.

435

436 In contrast, sensors and helpers in the NRC network of asterid plants are often genetically
437 dispersed even though they have a common evolutionary origin and belong to defined
438 phylogenetic clades (Wu *et al.*, 2017) (**Figure 2**). For example, all NRC-dependent sensors fall in
439 an expanded clade that includes many well-known resistance (R) proteins from different
440 solanaceous plant species, while the NRC helpers form a tight and well-supported sister clade. Wu
441 *et al.* (2017) proposed that this network dates back to ~100 million years and probably originated
442 from a pair of sensor/helper genes, which itself likely evolved from a singleton (**Figure 1, Figure**
443 **2**) (Adachi *et al.*, 2019b; Adachi & Kamoun, 2022; Wu *et al.*, 2017)..

444

445 Another well-studied NLR network is the TIR-NLR/CC_R-NLR network where helper NLRs like
446 NRG1 and ADR1 execute the hypersensitive response following pathogen activation of TIR-NLR
447 sensors. Remarkably, both TIR NLRs and CC_R NLRs form well-supported phylogenetic clades,
448 although they may not have a common evolutionary origin. It is tempting to hypothesize that this
449 network evolved from the pairing of single TIR-NLR and CC_R-NLR genes that associated with
450 additional signaling components (Liu *et al.*, 2023).

451

452 In the future, the phylogenetic position of NLRs, combined with the presence or absence of
 453 functional sequence motifs, occurrence of integrated domains and other variables should prove
 454 useful in categorizing NLRs into functional classes and revealing new pairs and networks from
 455 naïve plant genomes (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Adachi *et al.*, 2019b). Indeed, one of the challenges posed
 456 by the rapid acceleration in sequencing plant genomes is making sense of their NLR alphabet soup.
 457 Ultimately, we will be able to integrate multiple parameters to determine the network architecture
 458 of any given plant species, and to validate the predicted functional links between the NLRs.
 459

460

461 **Figure 2: Phylogenetics of NLR networks.**

462

463 (A) NLR networks exhibit a distinct phylogenetic structure with sensors and helpers belonging to well-
464 supported clades. In the NRC super-clade network, NRC-sensors (light orange) group into an expanded
465 clade whereas NRC-helpers (dark orange) form a tighter sister clade. The CC_R NLR clade helpers (blue),
466 which are paired with TIR-NLRs (green) sensors also belong to well-supported clades. The Phylogenetic
467 tree is based on the NB-ARC domain extracted from the NLRome of 9 selected species representing poales,
468 asterids, caryophyllales and rosids. The phylogenetic relationship of NLRs was inferred by approximately-
469 maximum-likelihood model using FastTree. The branches of the NLR tree are colored according to species,
470 as indicated in the species overview tree. CC_{G10} , CC_R , TIR NLR and CC NLR (including NRC sensors and
471 helpers) clades are outlined and respective bootstrap values for each main branch are provided. Arrows
472 indicate functional connections between clades. The position of the CC_R and TIR NLR as neighbouring
473 clades doesn't necessarily reflect a common phylogenetic origin and can be due to divergence of the other
474 deep branches in the NLR phylogeny. (B) While paired NLR sensors and helpers, derived from duplication
475 and diversification, tend to be genetically linked, the sensors and helpers of NLR networks can be
476 genetically dispersed.

477

478 **Functional consequences of genetically dispersed NLR networks**

479

480 Both the NRC network and the TIR-NLR/ CC_R -NLR network are genetically dispersed NLR
481 genes in contrast to the majority of paired NLRs. Does the lack of genetic linkage of networked
482 NLRs confer an evolutionary advantage? It is possible that genetically unlinked NLR networks
483 allow for the generation of more regulatory diversity or for the acquisition of novel domains, such
484 as the SD domain found in many NRC-dependent sensors or the multiple TIR-NLRs with
485 integrated domains (**Figure 1, Figure 3**) (Kourelis *et al.*, 2021; Seong *et al.*, 2020). In these
486 networks, which mediate recognition of multiple pathogens, the occurrence of the sensor genes
487 across several genome locations might facilitate birth-and-death evolution, enabling modular gene
488 loss when selection pressure against one pathogen is relieved, without affecting resistance to other
489 pathogens.

490

491 It is possible that helper NLR genetic redundancy combined with the convergence of multiple
492 sensors into one downstream helper facilitates the loss of genetic linkage over evolutionary time,
493 in contrast to paired NLRs where a sensor exclusively functions with a single helper. How these
494 NLR networks became unlinked and how they have adapted to the lack of co-regulation provided

495 by genetic linkage is not understood. These genetically dispersed NLR networks add another layer
496 of complexity to the evolutionary paradigm of the gene-for-gene model, as sensor NLRs (typically,
497 the *R* genes) are simultaneously co-evolving with pathogen effectors as well as with their
498 downstream helpers.

499

500 Despite the above considerations, genetically dispersed NLR networks can carry trade-offs for the
501 plant. For instance, NLR mis-regulation can result in autoimmunity, particularly when plants from
502 different populations are crossed (Atanasov *et al.*, 2018; Bomblies *et al.*, 2007; Chae *et al.*, 2014). This
503 phenomenon known as Dangerous Mix (DM) results in so-called hybrid necrosis and can be due
504 to a mismatch between genetically unlinked NLR gene loci. In one case, autoimmunity is triggered
505 by a heterocomplex between two *Arabidopsis* TIR-NLR proteins DM1 (DM1^{Uk-3}) and DM2d
506 (DM2d^{Uk-1}) that are encoded by genes on different chromosomes (Tran *et al.*, 2017).

507

508 **Pathogen activation of NLR functional singletons**

509

510 While the first plant NLR genes were cloned about 30 years ago (Whitham *et al.*, 1994, Bent *et al.*,
511 1994), the molecular mechanisms of NLR activation and immune signaling following pathogen
512 perception were only elucidated recently. Using cryo-electron microscopy, Wang and colleagues
513 obtained structural insights into the *Arabidopsis* singleton NLR ZAR1 before and after activation
514 (Wang *et al.*, 2019a; Wang *et al.*, 2019b). Following effector perception, ZAR1 undergoes a series
515 of conformational changes largely mediated by the NB-ARC domain (Wang *et al.*, 2019b). This
516 involves the exchange of ADP for ATP and ultimately leads to ZAR1 oligomerization and
517 assembly into a pentameric wheel-like homo-oligomer, analogous to the mammalian
518 inflammasome. This plant NLR oligomer was coined as the resistosome (Hu *et al.*, 2020; Hu *et al.*,
519 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2019a; Wang *et al.*, 2019b; Xiao *et al.*, 2023; Zhang *et al.*, 2015). NLR
520 oligomerization leads to induced proximity of the N-terminal signaling domains. In the case of the
521 CC-NLR ZAR1, the α 1-helix of the CC domain containing the N-terminal MADA-motif flips out
522 upon activation, forming a funnel-like structure that mediates resistosome insertion into the
523 plasma membrane (**Figure 3**) (Bi *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2019a). Following insertion, the ZAR1
524 resistosome presumably acts as a calcium channel, an activity that is required for the hypersensitive
525 cell death (Bi *et al.*, 2021). More recently, the ZAR1 oligomerisation model has expanded to
526 additional MADA-motif containing CC-NLRs from distantly related plant species. The two
527 functional singleton CC-NLR Sr35 from wheat and RPP7 from *Arabidopsis* were shown to

528 oligomerise into pentameric resistosome complexes revealing a general mechanism of MADA-
529 CC-NLR activations (Förderer *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2020; Zhao *et al.*, 2022).

530

531 **Pathogen activation in the NRC network**

532

533 How does the resistosome activation model identified for singleton CC-NLRs translate to CC-
534 NLR pairs or networks (**Box 1**)? Recent biochemical studies centered on NRC2 and NRC4
535 revealed that sensor-helper pairs in the NRC network employ an activation-and-release
536 mechanism, in which effector perception by sensor NLRs induces oligomerization and
537 resistosome formation of downstream helpers (**Figure 3**). The sensor does not appear to
538 oligomerize nor integrates into the helper resistosome (Ahn *et al.*, 2023; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b).
539 NRC2 was shown to oligomerize when activated by multiple NRC2-dependent sensor NLRs,
540 including the *Potato virus X* (PVX) R protein Rx, the bacterial R protein Bs2 and the oomycete R
541 proteins Rpi-amr1 and Rpi-amr3 (Ahn *et al.*, 2023; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b). The NRC2 oligomer is
542 composed of multiple NRC2 units and has a size consistent with a pentameric complex. Following
543 activation, NRC2 shifts from the cytoplasm to the plasma membrane, presumably to act as a
544 calcium channel as previously described for other CC-NLRs (**Figure 3**) (Ahn *et al.*, 2023; Contreras
545 *et al.*, 2023b). The activation-and-release model contrasts with the activation mechanisms of
546 metazoan paired NLRs, such as NAIP/NLRC4, which assemble into a heteromeric inflammasome
547 upon activation, indicating that plant and metazoan NLR pairs and networks may exhibit distinct
548 activation mechanisms (Contreras *et al.*, 2023b; Hu *et al.*, 2015; Vance, 2015).

549 The activation-and-release model further supports the notion that helper NLRs of the NRC
550 network functionally specialize in immune signaling by retaining an intact N-terminal MADA
551 motif and oligomerizing into resistosomes (Adachi *et al.*, 2019a; Adachi *et al.*, 2019b). In contrast,
552 NRC-dependent sensors have diverged from the ancestral state by specializing in pathogen
553 perception, while no longer retaining the MADA motif nor the capacity to oligomerize or form
554 resistosomes (**Figure 3**).

555

556 NRC-dependent sensors are not compatible with every NRC helper and exhibit a degree of
557 specificity as illustrated by the network architecture (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b;
558 Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wu *et al.*, 2017). While some sensors, such as Rx, Bs2 and Rpi-amr3 can
559 signal indistinctly through NRC2, NRC3 or NRC4, other sensors exhibit a narrower helper
560 specificity profile (Wu *et al.*, 2017). For example, Rpi-amr1 can signal through NRC2 but not NRC4
561 and conversely, Rpi-blb2 can signal through NRC4 but not NRC2 (Duggan *et al.*, 2021; Witek *et al.*,

2021; Wu *et al.*, 2017) (**Figure 3**). Notably, these differential genetic dependencies could be recapitulated biochemically in the form of NRC helper oligomerization given that sensors can only oligomerize helpers they can productively signal through (Ahn *et al.*, 2023; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b) (**Figure 3**). This supports the notion that networked immune receptor arrangements are more than mere genetic redundancies, as NRC helpers appear to exhibit a degree of functional specialization. The molecular determinants for sensor-helper compatibility or lack thereof, however, are not understood. Elucidating the molecular basis of sensor-helper communication can yield new opportunities for engineering efficient NLR networks that confer more robust disease resistance.

571

The activation-and-release biochemical model for sensor-helper pairs in the NRC network has provided a new conceptual framework for networked CC-NLR activation. NRC-dependent sensors do not appear to form resistosomes and instead mediate downstream NRC activation and oligomerization upon pathogen perception. NRC helpers engage in resistosome formation and immune signaling, forming resistosomes that do not include the sensor (Ahn *et al.*, 2023; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b). However, how exactly activated sensor NLRs in the NRC network communicate with their downstream helpers for the formation of a helper resistosome remains an unsolved question. One hypothesis is that direct sensor-helper interactions trigger helper oligomerization via the formation of transient sensor-helper intermediate complexes. Alternatively, the sensors may be communicating with downstream helpers indirectly via unknown signaling partners or by producing signaling molecules (**Box 1**).

583

584 **NLR activation in the TIR-NLRs/CC_R-NLR network**

585

TIR-NLRs form a receptor network with helper NLRs of the CC_R clade. This receptor network is phylogenetically structured in the sense that the sensors (TIR-NLRs) and helpers (CC_R-NLR) belong to well defined clades in the NLR tree (**Figure 2, Figure 3**). In this network, TIR-NLRs are thought to rely on their CC_R-NLR helpers to cause the hypersensitive cell death. The structures of the activated TIR-NLRs Roq1 and RPP1, revealed that these distinct TIR-NLRs also employ oligomerization-based activation mechanisms. Following effector perception, both immune receptors form homo-tetrameric resistosomes in which the TIR domains are brought together (Ma *et al.*, 2020; Martin *et al.*, 2020).

594

595 TIR-NLR resistosomes function as holo-enzymes, producing a range of small molecules which
596 include 2'-(5"-phosphoribosyl)-5'-ADP (pRib-ADP) or pRib-AMP as well as ADP-ribosylated
597 ATP/ADPR (ADPr-ATP/diADPR) (Huang *et al.*, 2022; Jia *et al.*, 2022) (**Figure 3**). These small
598 molecules are, in turn, perceived by a downstream signaling hub, comprised of the lipase-like
599 proteins EDS1 (enhanced disease susceptibility 1), PAD4 (phytoalexin deficient 4) and SAG101
600 (senescence-associated gene 101). Upon activation of upstream TIR-NLRs, EDS1 forms mutually
601 exclusive hetero-dimers with SAG101 or PAD4. The small molecule profile generated by the
602 upstream activated TIR-NLRs determines which EDS1 hetero-dimer is formed (Huang *et al.*, 2022;
603 Jia *et al.*, 2022) (**Figure 3**). The EDS1 signaling hub activates downstream helper CC_R-NLRs,
604 NRG1 and ADR1, with these helpers ultimately mediating the induction of cell death. EDS1-
605 SAG101 heterodimers form a complex with NRG1 leading to its oligomerization into an NRG1-
606 EDS1-SAG101 complex (Feehan *et al.*, 2023; Sun *et al.*, 2021) (**Figure 3**). Although multiple groups
607 have independently reported oligomerization of activated NRG1 (Feehan *et al.*, 2023; Jacob *et al.*,
608 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023b), whether EDS1-SAG101 associates with NRG1 oligomers stably,
609 transiently or in a timepoint-dependent manner, remains to be determined.

610

611 In contrast to EDS1-SAG101, EDS1-PAD4 heterodimers, associate with ADR1 and ADR1-like
612 proteins (Huang *et al.*, 2022). Activated NRG1 and ADR1 complexes then associate with the
613 plasma membrane to act as calcium channels (Jacob *et al.*, 2021; Saile *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023b).
614 Interestingly, NRG1 and ADR1 exhibit functional specialization. Not all TIR-NLRs can signal
615 through both helpers (Castel *et al.*, 2019; Wu *et al.*, 2019) (**Figure 3**). Moreover, NRG1 and ADR1
616 contribute differentially to immunity. While both mediate transcriptional reprogramming
617 downstream of activation, NRG1 appears to be partially specialized in cell death induction, while
618 ADR1 contributes to basal immunity and defence, independent of cell death (Saile *et al.*, 2020).
619 Considering that different TIR-NLRs activate different downstream helper CC_R-NLR, how exactly
620 the enzymatic activity of different TIR-NLRs is decoded by the EDS1 node is not yet clear.
621 Moreover, the functional determinants of diversification and the interplay between NRG1 and
622 ADR1 in immunity is not fully understood.

623

624

625 **Figure 3: NLR activation mechanisms.**

626

627 **Singleton:** Upon direct or indirect effector perception, singleton CC-NLRs such as ZAR1 and Sr35 activate
 628 via forming homo pentameric complexes termed resistosomes. Resistosomes accumulate at the plasma
 629 membrane to initiate immune signaling and mediate programmed hypersensitive cell death, presumably by
 630 acting as calcium channels. **NRC network:** The NRC PRR/NLR network employs an activation-and-
 631 release mechanism. Sensor NLRs activate upon perceiving their cognate effectors and relay an unknown
 632 signal to their downstream helper NRCs, leading to their oligomerization. These resistosome-like NRC
 633 homo-oligomers accumulate at the plasma membrane, separate from the sensors which activated them.
 634 The NRC network also features atypical modulator NLRs like NRCx, which can regulate signaling of the
 635 NRC helpers NRC2 and NRC3. The functional specialization into sensors and helpers greatly enhances
 636 immune receptor evolvability. For example, some sensor NLRs have acquired N-terminal SDs involved in
 637 pathogen sensing. Although PRRs such as Cf4 and Ve1 have been shown to require NRC3 for cell death
 638 induction, whether they activate helpers directly or whether there is a sensor NLR mediating PRR-helper
 639 NLR communication is not known. **NRG1/ADR1 network:** TIR-NLR singletons and pairs form
 640 tetrameric resistosomes upon activation. These resistosomes act as holoenzymes, producing a range of
 641 small molecules which are perceived by downstream lipase-like protein dimers EDS1-PAD4 and EDS1-
 642 SAG101. These activated EDS1-PAD4 and EDS1-SAG101 complexes can interact with the helper CC-
 643 NLRs ADR1 and NRG1, respectively, leading to their oligomerization into CCR-NLR resistosomes.
 644 Following their activation and oligomerization, the ADR1 and NRG1 resistosomes accumulate on the PM

645 to act as calcium-permeable channels, leading to immune signaling and hypersensitive cell death. This
646 network also features an atypical modulator NLR, NRG1c, which can negatively regulate immune signaling
647 by full length NRG1. TIR-NLRs, such as the CSA1/CHS3 pair, can act downstream of PRRs. The
648 EDS1/PAD4/ADR1 node, and to a lesser degree the EDS1/SAG101/NRG1 node, have also been shown
649 to act downstream of various PRRs.

650

651 **Cell biology of NLR resistosomes**

652

653 Although we still lack a detailed understanding of the cell biology of these immune receptors,
654 much progress has been made in recent years. NLRs can exhibit distinct subcellular localizations
655 in their inactive as well as their activated states, as reviewed in depth by Lüdke, Shepherd and
656 colleagues (Lüdke *et al*, 2022; Shepherd *et al*, 2023). For sensor NLRs these localizations can be
657 rationalized with the need to efficiently detect effector molecules, which in turn can target distinct
658 subcellular compartments in the host (Duggan *et al.*, 2021; Petre *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al*, 2018). One
659 well described example is the previously discussed TIR-NLR pair RRS1/RPS4 which recognizes
660 the activity of effectors that manipulate WRKY TFs (Deslandes *et al*, 2002; Le Roux *et al.*, 2015;
661 Sarris *et al.*, 2015). The inhibited RRS1/RPS4 complex associates with chromatin in the nucleus
662 and is activated upon effector interaction and modification of the RRS1 WRKY domain (Birker *et*
663 *al*, 2009; Huh *et al*, 2017; Le Roux *et al.*, 2015; Narusaka *et al*, 2009; Sarris *et al.*, 2015; Williams *et al*,
664 2014). Moreover, some sensor NLRs are required to associate with host guardees or decoys, which
665 themselves may exhibit specific subcellular localizations. Examples include the well-known CC-
666 NLRs RPM1 and RPS5, both of which guard plasma membrane-associated host immune
667 components and therefore require a plasma membrane localization prior to activation to be
668 functional (El Kasmi *et al*, 2017; Pottinger & Innes, 2020).

669 In the NRG1/ADR1 network, helper NLRs also exhibit diverse localizations and have been
670 shown to dynamically re-localize upon activation. The ADR1 and NRG1 family of helper CC-
671 NLRs, which act downstream of TIR-NLRs, were both shown to reside in the cytoplasm as well
672 as in the PM in their inactive state (Saile *et al.*, 2021). In addition, inactive NRG1A and NRG1B
673 were also reported to localize to the endoplasmic reticulum (Wu *et al.*, 2019). Upon TIR-NLR
674 signalling, ADR1 and NRG1 both form higher molecular complexes that shift their localization,
675 forming puncta at the plasma membrane (Feehan *et al.*, 2023; Saile *et al.*, 2021). Both, localization
676 and functionality, of NRG1 and ADR1 helpers are phospholipid dependent, as depletion of
677 phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate results in mis-localization and a loss of cell death activity (Saile
678 *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023b). However, a re-localization of NRG1 to the nucleus was also

679 reported upon activation (Feehan *et al.*, 2023). It remains to be determined what the direct function
680 of NRG1 in the nucleus could be. However, the shift from a cytoplasmic to a membrane associated
681 localization has also been described for the singleton NLR ZAR1 (Bi *et al.*, 2021), further outlining
682 that subcellular shift towards the plasma membrane could be a general feature of singleton and
683 helper NLRs. Whether this is related to the calcium channel activity of the resistosomes remains
684 unclear (**Box 1**).

685 In the NRC network, the localization of sensors and helpers also plays an important role. The R
686 protein Rpi-blb2 is an NRC4-dependent sensor NLR which confers resistance to strains of the
687 oomycete *Phytophthora infestans* carrying the effector AVRblb2 (Bozkurt *et al.*, 2011; Wu *et al.*, 2017).
688 Recently, Duggan and colleagues (2021) showed that during infection with the *P. infestans* and in
689 the absence of activation, NRC4 focally accumulates at the extra-haustorial membrane (EHM),
690 where effectors are delivered into the host cell and AVRblb2 accumulates during pathogen
691 infection (Duggan *et al.*, 2021). Following activation, NRC4 loses this focal perihastorial
692 localisation and accumulates as puncta spread throughout the PM, triggering cell death presumably
693 due to the formation oligomeric resistosomes (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a; Contreras *et al.*, 2023b;
694 Duggan *et al.*, 2021). Distinct NLRs display a degree of specificity in their localization given that
695 focal haustorial accumulation is specific to NRC4 and not its paralog NRC2 nor the singleton CC-
696 NLR ZAR1 (Duggan *et al.*, 2021). Sensors co-evolve with their matching effectors and may have
697 to adapt to their localization to capture the effector. Helpers, in turn, may also evolve specialized
698 localization patterns to match their sensors, to enable effective sensor signaling. Interestingly, most
699 *P. infestans* sensors characterised to date are NRC4-dependent, so it is perhaps not surprising that
700 NRC4 has acquired a focal localization around an infection structure produced by this oomycete
701 pathogen (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wu *et al.*, 2018). In addition, the NRC2 helper forms fibril-like
702 structures at the EHM during the interaction with *P. infestans* and may therefore contribute in a
703 different way to immunity against *P. infestans* (Duggan *et al.*, 2021).

704 Although the details of how networked CC-NLR sensors communicate and activate their
705 downstream helpers remain unclear, it can be assumed that a certain degree of subcellular
706 proximity is required for efficient signal transmission. Recent work on the sensor Rx and its helper
707 NRC2 demonstrates that they co-localize in the cytoplasm in the absence of the coat protein
708 effector molecule from *Potato virus X* (Contreras *et al.*, 2023b). Activation of the system leads to a
709 shift in localization to plasma membrane puncta for the NRC2 helper resistosome, while Rx
710 remains cytoplasmic (Contreras *et al.*, 2023b). The formation of puncta and a re-localization to the
711 plasma membrane has also been reported for activated ZAR1 and NRC4 (Duggan *et al.*, 2021).

712 What determines the subcellular localization of helper NLRs pre- or post-activation? Domain swap
713 experiments involving the N-terminal CC-domain of NRC2 and NRC4 demonstrated that this can
714 lead to a shift in localization for these helper NLRs in their inactive state (Duggan et al., 2021).
715 Thus, the N-terminal CC domain appears to play an important role in determining the localization
716 of NLR helpers, possibly due to interaction with membranes of various composition. Moreover,
717 it is still unclear what the nature or function of the observed punctate structures are or whether
718 they represent molecular condensates or macro-complexes of activated resistosomes. The diversity
719 of NLR localizations and their dynamic re-localization following receptor activation is another
720 example of the remarkable functional diversity exhibited by these proteins (**Box 1**).

721

722 **Atypical NLRs: modulators of plant immunity**

723

724 An emerging concept in NLR network biology is that NLRs can modulate the activity of other
725 NLRs in configurations that don't match the conventional model of sensor/helper pairing. The
726 first reports of this phenomenon were classic examples of genetically linked sensor-helper pairs
727 where the sensor can suppress a constitutively active helper, as is the case for the RGA5/RGA4
728 and RRS1/RPS4 pairs discussed above (Césari *et al.*, 2014; Ma *et al.*, 2018). More recently, two
729 studies identified NLR modulators, which cannot be classified into the conventional categories of
730 sensor, executor, or helper. Rather, these atypical NLRs function as modulators of NLR signaling
731 (Adachi *et al.*, 2023a; Wu *et al.*, 2022). The *NRG1* NLR gene cluster in *Arabidopsis* consists of
732 *NRG1a*, *NRG1b* and *NRG1c*, also termed *NRG1.1*, *NRG1.2* and *NRG1.3* respectively (Wu *et al.*,
733 2022). As described above, *NRG1a/b* proteins are well-known helper NLRs required for immune
734 signaling and induction of cell death downstream of TIR-NLRs. Both *NRG1a* and *NRG1b*
735 contain all features of canonical NLRs, an N-terminal CC_R domain, central NB-ARC and C-
736 terminal LRR domain. *NRG1c*, on the other hand, is a truncated NLR lacking a CC_R domain and
737 most of the NB-ARC thus making it unlikely to function as a helper NLR. In contrast, *NRG1c*
738 can negatively regulate *NRG1a/b* signaling and cell death, presumably by competing with
739 *NRG1a/b* proteins for interaction with EDS1/SAG101 complexes. However, *NRG1c* can also
740 negatively regulate autoimmune variants of *NRG1a* which trigger cell death in an EDS1-
741 independent manner meaning that the precise mechanism by which *NRG1c* immunomodulates
742 *NRG1a/b* requires further investigations (Wu *et al.*, 2022) (**Figure 3**).

743

744 Another NLR modulator is NRCx, a full-length CC-NLR which phylogenetically clusters with
745 helper NRCs and is closely related to NRC2 and NRC3. Similar to other NRCs, NRCx has the

746 classic tripartite domain architecture of CC, NB-ARC and LRR domains. However, unlike other
747 NRCs, the NRCx N-terminal MADA sequence is non-functional and unable to trigger cell death
748 when swapped for functional MADA N-termini (Adachi *et al.*, 2023a). NRCx is also unusual for
749 an NLR as its silencing results in autoimmunity in *N. benthamiana*. This autoimmunity is partially
750 dependent on the NRC family members NRC2 and NRC3, but not NRC4, with NRCX silencing
751 leading to enhanced cell death by NRC2 and NRC3, but not NRC4 (Adachi *et al.*, 2023a). This
752 points to NRCX as an immunomodulating component in the NRC network, specifically capable
753 of regulating the function of NRC2 and NRC3 (**Figure 3**). Considering its evolutionary relatedness
754 with NRC2 and NRC3, it is tempting to speculate that NRCX arose during NRC evolution to
755 temper the activity of the NRCs, possibly during particular stages of plant development and to
756 avoid inappropriate activation of the PRR/NLR pathway mediated by these helper NLRs (Adachi
757 *et al.*, 2023a). The precise biochemical mechanisms by which NRCX negatively regulates the NRC2
758 and NRC3 helpers remain unknown and await further research.

759

760 NRG1c and NRCx are atypical NLRs because they act as NLR modulators within their respective
761 NLR networks. It is possible that the complex network configurations that arose throughout
762 evolution resulted in novel NLR functional specializations to maintain network homeostasis and
763 block mis-regulation. Genetically dispersed NLR networks are probably more prone to mis-
764 activation and may be more difficult to regulate, therefore, NLR modulators may have emerged
765 to regulate increasingly complex signaling architectures (**Box 1**). Understanding the molecular
766 mechanisms by which modulator NLRs function will shed light on how networked signaling
767 architectures are regulated. Moreover, this knowledge may enable new avenues for bioengineering
768 more efficient signaling in plant immunity by altering the function, intensity, or specificity of the
769 immunomodulators.

770

771 **Tissue and cell specificity of NLR proteins**

772

773 Effective deployment of plant immunity can be achieved through tissue and cell specific responses.
774 However, in sharp contrast to animal immunity (Weisberg *et al.*, 2021), our understanding of plant
775 immunity, including NLR biology, at the tissue and cell resolution is limited. Only few studies
776 examined expression patterns of NLR genes across different plant tissues. In Arabidopsis, the
777 majority of NLRs are more highly expressed in shoot compared to root tissue. In contrast, legumes
778 and monocots have overall higher expression levels of NLR genes in roots compared to shoots
779 (Munch *et al.*, 2018). Tissue/organ specific NLR expression patterns may reflect a resistance

780 response to pathogens that attack specific tissues (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2011). Tissue
781 specific expression of NLR genes may also reduce the risk of inadvertent activation of immune
782 responses in certain tissue types, given that NLR mis-regulation can lead to adverse effects
783 (Bombliès *et al.*, 2007; Palma *et al.*, 2010).

784

785 Tissue specific upregulation of expression of immune receptors could contribute to an effective
786 and specific response to pathogen attack. NLRs, especially TIR-type NLRs, can show induced
787 expression during pathogen infection thereby enhancing general immunity or priming the immune
788 system (Mohr *et al.*, 2010; Tian *et al.*, 2021; Yu *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, Adachi and colleagues (2023)
789 reported that some NRC helper genes are induced following pathogen infection. NRC2a and
790 NRC2b were upregulated following treatment of *N. benthamiana* leaves with the non-pathogenic
791 *Pseudomonas fluorescens* while other NRC genes such as NRC3 and NRC4a/b and the
792 immunomodulator NRCx remained unchanged. This marked shift in balance of NRC2a/b to
793 NRCx expression may contribute to more robust immune responses (Adachi *et al.*, 2023a). RNA-
794 sequencing of *N. benthamiana* roots, leaves and flowers/buds revealed that while NRC2, NRC3,
795 NRC4 and NRCx were expressed in all three tissues, other NRCs, such as NRC7a and NRC8b,
796 were mainly expressed in roots and not in other tissues. (Adachi *et al.*, 2023a). How potential tissue
797 or cell-type-specific expression and induction of NLR genes contributes to enhancing robustness
798 and efficiency of plant immune responses is not yet understood.

799

800 To what degree do NLRs exhibit cell-type specificity (**Box 1**)? With the advent of single cell RNA-
801 sequencing techniques, cell specific expression patterns of immune receptors in plants can be
802 elucidated. Recently, Tang and colleagues (2023) demonstrated that in *Arabidopsis* some TIR-
803 NLR proteins show specific expression in cells of the vasculature. In addition, treatment with the
804 fungal pathogen *Colletotrichum higginsianum* resulted in upregulation of NLRs specifically in vascular
805 tissues (Tang *et al.*, 2023). These observations would be in line with cell-layer specific immune
806 responses observed in plant roots under pathogen threat (Chuberre *et al.*, 2018; Fröschel *et al.*, 2021;
807 Rich-Griffin *et al.*, 2020), and the vascular-specific hypersensitive cell death observed in
808 Brassicaceae against the bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris* (Kamoun *et al.*, 1992).

809

810 The mechanisms that drive tissue or cell type specific expression patterns remain largely unknown.
811 In addition to specific promoters and epigenetic regulation of expression (Le *et al.*, 2015; Tsuchiya
812 & Eulgem, 2013), NLR transcript levels are also influenced by small RNAs (Zhai *et al.*, 2011; Zhang
813 *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, specific E3 ligases can also control protein levels of NLRs post-

814 transcriptionally (Wu *et al*, 2020). Whether these mechanisms can create tissue or cell-type specific
815 patterns of NLRs remains to be tested. The elucidation of NLR expression patterns at the cellular
816 resolution will further our understanding of NLR networks and enable a more efficient
817 deployment of NLRs in agriculture.

818

819 **Crosstalk between cell surface immune receptors and NLRs**

820

821 In addition to NLRs, plants detect pathogens through cell surface pattern recognition receptors
822 (PRRs), which consist of two major classes of trans-membrane proteins: receptor proteins (RPs)
823 and receptor kinases (RKs). RPs carry a small cytoplasmic tail, but unlike RKs they lack a C-
824 terminal kinase domain. Similar to NLRs, RPs and RKs are also known to form receptor networks
825 (Smakowska-Luzan *et al*, 2018; Wu *et al*, 2018). Following perception of pathogen-derived
826 molecules, RPs and RKs hetero-oligomerize with co-receptor RKs, such as the LRR-RK
827 SERK3/BAK1, which activates downstream signaling by phosphorylating downstream RLCKs to
828 result in an immune response, generally known as PRR-triggered immunity (PTI) (Ngou *et al*,
829 2022a; Zhang *et al*, 2023).

830

831 Traditionally, PRRs and NLRs were thought to induce distinct immune pathways. However, there
832 is intricate crosstalk between the signaling pathways induced by cell surface and intracellular
833 immune receptors. Indeed, PRRs and NLRs mutually potentiate each other by enhancing
834 transcription of the core signaling components of these pathways (Ngou *et al*, 2021; Yuan *et al*,
835 2021). Specifically, the capacity of some NLRs to activate hypersensitive cell death in response to
836 effectors is compromised in the absence of cell surface immune signaling. Examples include
837 activation of the RRS1/RPS4 TIR-NLR pair by the bacterial effector AvrRps4, activation of the
838 CC_{G10}-NLRs RPS2 and RPS5 by AvrRpt2 and AvrPphB respectively, and activation of the CC-
839 NLR RPM1 by AvrRpm1 (Ngou *et al*, 2021; Yuan *et al*, 2021). Recent work has shown that cell-
840 surface and intracellular immune receptor repertoires across plant species concertedly expand and
841 contract. This suggests that they are potentially co-evolving and/or functionally inter-dependent,
842 in support of the mutual potentiation model mentioned above (Ngou *et al*, 2022b).

843

844 NLRs can also act genetically downstream of cell surface immune receptor activation. In
845 Arabidopsis, the EDS1/PAD4/ADR1 and, to a lesser extent, EDS1/SAG101/NRG1 modules
846 are genetically required for a subset of the immune responses triggered by LRR-RPs and LRR-
847 RKs (Pruitt *et al*, 2021; Tian *et al*, 2021) (**Figure 3**). Some cell-surface RPs can trigger a

848 hypersensitive response that is indistinguishable from the NLR-mediated cell death response. In
849 tomato, the RPs Cf-4, Cf-9, Cf-2 and Cf-5 recognize apoplastic secreted effectors of the fungus
850 *Cladosporium fulvum*, while Ve1 recognizes the effector Ave1 from fungi of the *Verticillium* genus
851 (De Jonge *et al.*, 2012; Luderer *et al.*, 2002; Rivas & Thomas, 2005; Seear & Dixon, 2003). Helper
852 NLRs of the NRC family are required for the hypersensitive cell death mediated by these RPs
853 (Fradin *et al.*, 2009; Gabriëls *et al.*, 2006; Gabriëls *et al.*, 2007; Kourelis *et al.*, 2022). Recent work by
854 Kourelis *et al.* involving a combination of *nrc2/3/4* KO plants and genetic complementation
855 revealed that NRC3 is the primary helper NLR required for the hypersensitive response induced
856 by the Cf receptors (Kourelis *et al.*, 2022) (**Figure 3**). EDS1 was also shown to be required for full
857 Ve1 and Cf4-mediated immunity, implying that the NRG1/ADR1 network may also be involved
858 in signaling for these cell-surface receptors (Fradin *et al.*, 2009; Kourelis *et al.*, 2022). If this is the
859 case, at least two distinct NLR networks have evolved to contribute to cell-surface signaling in
860 solanaceous plants. Although it is tempting to speculate that sensor NLRs act as a bridge between
861 cell-surface receptors and downstream helpers, the precise molecular link between cell-surface
862 immunity and downstream helper NLRs for Cfs and Ve1 is not known (**Box 1**).

863

864 Considering the importance of cell-surface immunity and its synergy with intracellular immune
865 responses, it is not surprising that NLRs have evolved to guard cell surface receptors and their
866 downstream components. As mentioned previously the CC-type NLRs ZAR1 and Prf have
867 evolved to recognize bacterial effectors via interacting with RLCKs. ZAR1 engages with subfamily
868 XII-2 RLCKs, also called ZED1-related kinases (ZRKs) in *Arabidopsis* and *N. benthamiana*, while
869 Prf monitors the Pto kinase in tomato. (Adachi *et al.*, 2023b; Bombarely *et al.*, 2012; Laflamme *et*
870 *al.*, 2020; Lewis *et al.*, 2013; Ntoukakis *et al.*, 2014; Salmeron *et al.*, 1996; Schultink *et al.*, 2019; Seto
871 *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2015). The *Arabidopsis* NLR RPS5 and the unrelated barley (*Hordeum vulgare*)
872 NLR Pbr1 have converged on guarding PBS1-like RLCKs to recognise the bacterial effector
873 AvrPphB (Carter *et al.*, 2019). Recently, the CSA1/CHS3 TIR-NLR pair was shown to guard BAK1
874 and BIR3 homeostasis, triggering cell death upon sensing its perturbation (Schulze *et al.*, 2022).
875 Interestingly, cell death induced by the microbial pattern pg23 was found to be CSA1-dependent
876 (Schulze *et al.*, 2022; Yang *et al.*, 2022) (**Figure 3**). It is possible that NLR-dependency for cell death
877 or immunity of some PRRs could arise from guard-guardee NLR dynamics, where singleton or
878 sensor NLRs evolve to guard components of cell-surface immunity and subsequently become
879 necessary for the full function of their PRR gardees.

880

881 While much progress has been made in recent years towards understanding the functional links
882 between cell-surface and intracellular immunity, further studies should strive to study PRRs and
883 NLR receptors with an appreciation of their respective huge structural and functional diversity.
884 It's evident that distinct classes of cell-surface and intracellular receptors interact with each other
885 to different degrees and through different mechanisms. Moreover, it appears that many of the
886 connections between cell-surface and intracellular receptors may vary across species, while others
887 are conserved (Kourelis *et al.*, 2022). The full picture of the complex and interdependent nature of
888 plant immune system receptor networks will only be clarified once we integrate their structural
889 and evolutionary diversity.

890 **Pathogen suppression of NLRs by modulation of immune signaling pathways**

891 An emerging concept in NLR biology is that pathogen effectors can act as both triggers and
892 suppressors of NLR-triggered immunity. While most effectors studied to date suppress immune
893 pathways induced by PTI, in some cases, adapted pathogens deploy effectors to interfere with host
894 NLR signaling to promote disease (Wu & Derevnina, 2023). This effector-mediated suppression
895 of NLR signaling can be achieved by various mechanisms. Some effectors act indirectly, by
896 interfering with host proteins that contribute to NLR signaling pathways, while other act directly
897 by physically interacting with NLRs to perturb their function (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Karki *et al.*,
898 2021; Lopez *et al.*, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2023a)(**Figure 4**).

899
900 The effector AVRcap1b from *P. infestans* can indirectly suppress cell death mediated by the *N.*
901 *benthamiana* helper NLRs NRC2 and NRC3 by physically interacting with the host protein
902 NbTOL9a, a component of the endosomal sorting complex required for transport (ESCRT)
903 vesicle trafficking machinery (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Moulinier-Anzola *et al.*, 2020). NbTOL9a was
904 shown to act as a negative regulator of NRC2/3-mediated cell death (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021). While
905 the exact mechanism by which AVRcap1b-NbTOL9a interaction leads to suppression of NRC
906 function is unknown, AVRcap1b is presumably hijacking a negative regulator to compromise
907 NRC2/3-mediated immunity activities (**Figure 4**).

908
909 Another example is the *Xanthomonas euvesicatoria* effector XopQ, which can suppress NLR signaling
910 by targeting and directly binding TFT4, a protein of the 14-3-3 family that functions in immunity
911 downstream of NLR activation, presumably by interfering with TFT4-client interactions required
912 for correct immune signalling (Teper *et al.*, 2014).

913

914 The effector RipAC, from the bacteria *R. solanacearum* interferes with NLR signaling by associating
915 with SGT1, an important host regulator required for NLR homeostasis and function. By forming
916 a complex with SGT1, RipAC prevents MAPK-mediated phosphorylation of SGT1, which is
917 normally enhanced upon immune activation (Yu *et al*, 2020). RipAC-SGT1 complex formation
918 also prevents association between SGT1 and RAR1. SGT1, RAR1 and HSP90 normally form a
919 molecular chaperone ternary complex which is required for correct functionality of multiple NLRs
920 (Azevedo *et al*, 2006). This perturbation of SGT1 phosphorylation and SGT1-RAR1 complex
921 formation by RipAC can suppress immunity mediated by two SGT1-dependent NLRs, R3a and
922 RPS2, as well as immune signaling triggered by the *R. solanacearum* AVR effectors RipAA and RipP1
923 (Nakano *et al*, 2020; Yu *et al.*, 2020).

924

925 Another remarkable example is the HopBF1 effector from *P. syringae*. This effector can mimic a
926 host client of the NLR chaperone HSP90, binding HSP90 and phosphorylating it, which results
927 in its complete inactivation. As this chaperone is required to maintain NLRs in a stable, inactive
928 and signal-competent form, this phosphorylation results in compromised NLR signaling (Lopez
929 *et al.*, 2019).

930

931 Additional effectors that inhibit or suppress NLR pathways have been identified to date and are
932 listed in **Table 1**, however, in most cases their precise molecular mechanisms and host targets are
933 not yet fully known.

934

935 **Pathogen suppression of NLRs by direct inhibition**

936

937 Some effectors can suppress immunity by directly targeting NLR proteins (**Table 1**). The effector
938 HopZ3 from *P. syringae* is a YopJ family acetyltransferase that acetylates members of the CC-NLR
939 RPM1 immune complex, thereby inactivating its immune response and promoting pathogen
940 growth (Lee *et al*, 2015). Another example is the RHA1B effector from the root knot nematode
941 *Globodera pallida*, which functions as a E3 ubiquitin ligase that targets NLRs for degradation,
942 thereby suppressing immunity (Kud *et al*, 2019). More recently, additional studies revealed that
943 pathogen effectors can directly target helper NLRs to suppress immunity.

944

945 Two studies on the SS15 effector from the potato cyst nematode *Globodera rostochiensis* (Contreras
946 *et al.*, 2023a; Derevnina *et al.*, 2021) revealed that SS15 can inhibit cell death triggered by the helper

947 NLRs NRC2 and NRC3 as well as the tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) helper NLR NRC1 of the
948 solanaceous NRC network. SS15 acts as a proteinaceous inhibitor, directly binding to the HD1
949 region of the central NB-ARC domains of the helper NLRs (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a; Derevnina *et*
950 *al.*, 2021). SS15 was proposed to immobilize a critical “hinge” loop in the NB-ARC domain,
951 preventing intramolecular rearrangements required for activation and resistosome formation. As
952 a consequence, the inhibitor locks NRC proteins in an inactive conformation and prevents the
953 oligomerization and plasma membrane translocation that otherwise would follow activation by
954 upstream NRC-dependent sensors (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a).

955

956 A recent study on the bacterial effector AvrPtoB revealed that it can target helper NLRs in the
957 NRG1/ADR1 network for degradation. AvrPtoB has E3 ligase activity and can ubiquitinate and
958 promote degradation of ADR1-L1, while having similar but milder effects on ADR1-L2 (Wang *et*
959 *al.*, 2023a). This activity suppresses ADR1-L1 and ADR1-L2-mediated cell death. Interestingly,
960 AvrPtoB cannot suppress ADR1, and this specificity in helper NLR suppression appears to be
961 encoded in the N-terminal CC_R domain (Wang *et al.*, 2023a).

962

963 These two studies indicate that targeting helper NLRs that are central nodes in NLR networks is
964 a common virulence strategy (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a; Wang *et al.*, 2023a) (**Figure 4**). The fact that
965 three distantly related pathogens, an oomycete a nematode and a bacterium, have convergently
966 evolved effectors that suppress networked helper NLRs highlights how important NLR networks
967 are in mediating immunity against diverse pathogens (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023a).
968 Targeting helper NLRs is a favorable virulence mechanism for pathogens, given that shutting
969 down one helper node results in simultaneously compromising multiple upstream sensor NLRs
970 and cell surface receptors. This was demonstrated for AVRcap1b and SS15, since both could
971 suppress cell death triggered by the tomato cell-surface RP Cf-4 upon recognition of the fungal
972 effector Avr4, in addition to suppression of sensor NLRs (Kourelis *et al.*, 2022).

973

974 Indeed, networked signaling architectures are thought to increase robustness of the plant immune
975 system (Adachi 2022), and redundant nodes in the form of helper NLRs may help to evade
976 suppression by pathogen effectors. Notably, in all three cases, the host plant features additional
977 “backup” helper nodes that are insensitive to the effectors. For instance, both SS15 and AVRcap1b
978 can suppress *N. benthamiana* NRC2 and NRC3, but not their NRC4 paralog, whereas AvrPtoB
979 can suppress ADR1-L1 and ADR1-L2, but not ADR1 in Arabidopsis (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wang
980 *et al.*, 2023a).

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It is possible that some pathogens have evolved effectors that suppress all helper nodes simultaneously, therefore compromising an entire network in a given plant taxon. Such pathogens would then have a wide host range, and this could explain the anomalously extended host range of pathogens like *Phytophthora palmivora*, which has >100 host plant species (Carella *et al*, 2018; Erwin & Ribeiro, 1996). However, it should be noted that SS15, AVRcap1b and AvrPtoB also have AVR activities, meaning that they are recognized by particular plant genotypes. SS15 triggers cell death mediated by an unknown NLR in *Nicotiana tabacum* (Ali *et al*, 2015). AVRcap1b is recognized by Rpi-cap1 in *Solanum capsicibaccatum*, and while the underlying gene is unknown, it is hypothesized to be a TIR-type NLR (Verzaux *et al*, 2012). That would imply that Rpi-cap1 would recognize AVRcap1b through a signaling that is independent of the CC-NLR NRC network (Rietman, 2011; Verzaux *et al.*, 2012). This would be analogous to the TIR-NLR SNC1, which recognises the effector AvrPtoB. By guarding ADR1-L1/L2 helpers targeted for suppression by AvrPtoB, SNC1 activates immune signaling via ADR1, a helper that is insensitive to AvrPtoB (Wang *et al.*, 2023a). Therefore, just like other important nodes, helper NLRs can be guarded by particular NLRs in order to prevent pathogen interference.

998
 999

1000 **Figure 4: Mechanisms of pathogen suppression of NLR immune signaling.**

1001

1002 Pathogen effectors can suppress NLR signaling via diverse strategies. Some effectors can target downstream
1003 components required for NLR signaling to suppress immune signaling (**Table 1**) (**A**), while others can
1004 suppress immune responses by directly targeting NLRs (**B**). (**C**) In the NRC network, two effectors have
1005 been identified that can suppress immune signaling of multiple sensor NLRs by directly targeting their
1006 downstream helpers NRC2 and NRC3 (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021). The potato cyst nematode effector SS15
1007 acts as a proteinaceous inhibitor of NRC2/3, directly binding their NB-ARC domain to prevent their
1008 oligomerization (Contreras *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, the potato late blight pathogen effector AVRcap1b
1009 interacts with host protein NbTOL9a, a vesicle trafficking component, to suppress NRC2/3-mediated cell
1010 death via an unknown mechanism. NRC4 is not suppressed by these two effectors and can mediate immune
1011 signaling by many upstream sensors even in the presence of SS15 and AVRcap1b, highlighting the
1012 robustness provided by helper NLR redundancy in these networked architectures. (**D**) The bacterial
1013 effector AvrPtoB can suppress ADR1-L1 and ADR1-L2 by acting as an E3 ligase, targeting these helper
1014 NLRs for degradation (Wang *et al.*, 2023a). AVRpToB cannot suppress ADR1, another helper NLR. The
1015 sensor NLR SNC1 guards ADR1-L1/L2 and, upon detecting the activity of AvrPtoB, can activate
1016 immunity via ADR1, another example of how helper NLR network configuration can confer robustness
1017 to pathogen suppression.

1018

1019 **Effector suppression of NLRs: the dark matter of R gene discovery?**

1020

1021 How many R genes are cryptically present in crop genomes due to pathogen suppression (**Box 1**)?
1022 This is an exciting unanswered question raised by the discovery of effectors that suppress helper
1023 NLRs. R-gene discovery may have overlooked potential sources of resistance due to the presence
1024 of hitherto unknown NLR suppressors in the pathogen. This R-gene masking becomes even more
1025 of an issue whenever pathogens suppress helper NLRs, that are downstream nodes in networks
1026 of sensor NLRs and cell surface receptors (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a; Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et*
1027 *al.*, 2023a).

1028

1029 Pathogen NLR suppressors may also explain cases in which NLR genes could not be successfully
1030 transferred between plant families, a phenomenon known as restricted taxonomic functionality
1031 (RTF) (Tai *et al.*, 1999). While in some cases RTF may be due to missing genetic components in
1032 the heterologous plant, it is possible that species-specific pathogen suppressors could underpin
1033 the lack of functionality of some NLR across taxa. Future work should consider NLR-suppressing
1034 effectors and their potential contributions to RTF in R-gene discovery and disease resistance

1035 breeding pipelines in order to avoid overlooking a potentially vast and untapped reservoir of
1036 immune receptors.

1037

1038 **NLR bioengineering: new recognition specificities**

1039

1040 The deployment of R-genes in agriculture is often ineffective as pathogens tend to rapidly evolve
1041 to evade recognition. In addition, few R genes have been identified against the majority of
1042 economically important pathogens. This has fuelled attempts to bioengineer made-to-order NLR
1043 immune receptors to achieve durable and versatile disease resistance (Cesari *et al*, 2022; De la
1044 Concepcion *et al*, 2019; Farnham & Baulcombe, 2006; Förderer *et al*, 2022; Giannakopoulou *et al*,
1045 2015; Huang *et al*, 2021; Kim *et al*, 2016; Liu *et al*, 2021; Maidment *et al*, 2022; Segretin *et al*, 2014;
1046 Tamborski *et al*, 2023; Wang *et al*, 2021). This goal of designer R genes is often portrayed as the
1047 holy grail of plant pathology. Most attempts at NLR engineering to date have been aimed at
1048 obtaining novel disease resistance specificities, a topic that has been recently reviewed in depth by
1049 Marchal and colleagues (Marchal *et al*, 2022b). In particular, many approaches have focused on
1050 NLR-ID engineering, specifically by re-surfacing the structure of IDs by amino acid substitution
1051 or by swapping IDs for other closely related proteins to expand the effector recognition
1052 specificities of IDs (Bentham *et al*, 2022; Cesari *et al*, 2022; De la Concepcion *et al*, 2019; Liu *et al*,
1053 2021; Maidment *et al*, 2022).

1054

1055 The ortholog/allelic series of the *Oryza* (rice) NLR pair Pia carries at least 9 different integrations
1056 (IDs) in the Pia-2 (aka RGA5) sensor indicating that throughout evolution, an NLR scaffold can
1057 accommodate the fusion of domains of unrelated sequence (Shimizu *et al*, 2022). Indeed, in the
1058 Poaceae, the majority of NLR-IDs, including Pia-2, belong to 24 major clades (major integration
1059 clades or MIC) (Bailey *et al*, 2018). This has inspired NLR bioengineers: If nature can make NLR-
1060 IDs every few millions of years, why can't we do this in our laboratories? (Schornack & Kamoun,
1061 2023).

1062

1063 This view has even inspired bioengineers to integrate animal antibody domains into NLR proteins.
1064 In a recent proof-of-concept study, Kourelis and colleagues showed that the integrated HMA
1065 domain of the rice Pik-1 sensor NLR can be replaced with camelid-derived nanobodies, swapping
1066 the recognition specificity while retaining signaling via its downstream helper Pik-2 (Kourelis *et al*,
1067 2023). These engineered immune receptor pairs, termed pikobodies, can mount an effective
1068 immune response and virus resistance when activated with the fluorescent proteins (FPs) GFP

1069 and mCherry, leading to NLRs with completely synthetic recognition specificities. This work
1070 implies that NLRs could in theory be developed to recognise any antigen that bind nanobodies,
1071 combining animal adaptive immunity with plant innate immunity, and conferring a pseudo-
1072 adaptive immune system to plants. Transgenic plants expressing Pikobodies can confer resistance
1073 to FP-expressing strains of *Potato virus X* (PVX) to levels comparable to the natural disease
1074 resistance gene Rx (a CC_NLR) (Kourelis *et al.*, 2023). The Pikobody example of bioengineering
1075 highlights the importance of how fundamental knowledge of NLR function and evolution can
1076 guide approaches for disease resistance engineering. Indeed, the Pikobody system built on
1077 numerous studies on the genetics, biochemistry and, particularly, the evolution of the Pik-1/Pik-
1078 2 NLR pair and the integrated domain (Bialas *et al.*, 2021; De la Concepcion *et al.*, 2021; De la
1079 Concepcion *et al.*, 2018; Zdrzalek *et al.*, 2020). Nonetheless, we still don't understand how the Pik
1080 NLR pair gets activated in precise details, and further advances on the topic will undoubtedly help
1081 facilitate further bioengineering.

1082

1083 **NLR Bioengineering: resistance gene resurrection**

1084

1085 The occurrence of cryptic disease resistance genes in crop genomes as a consequence of effector
1086 suppression of NLRs opens up the possibility of engineering resilient immune receptors that evade
1087 pathogen inhibition. In a recent study, (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a) the authors leveraged their
1088 mechanistic understanding of how SS15 interferes with NRC activation to develop “effector-
1089 proof” NRC variants that evade suppression. To achieve this, they combined structural
1090 information of the inhibitor/NLR complex as well as sequence polymorphisms between inhibited
1091 and insensitive NLRs to generate a single amino acid variant of NRC2 that evades SS15 inhibition.
1092 This single amino acid variant has the capacity to activate cell death triggered by all tested upstream
1093 NRC2-dependent sensors in the absence and presence of SS15 (Contreras *et al.*, 2023a). This
1094 rescued upstream disease resistance genes are now “resurrected”, becoming able to respond to
1095 AVR effectors even when the inhibitor is present. This form of helper NLR bioengineering may
1096 be a highly effective strategy for achieving disease resistance, as it holds the potential of
1097 simultaneously restoring functionality (resurrecting) multiple upstream sensors. In the future, it
1098 will be interesting to apply this bioengineering strategy to other NLRs that are suppressed by
1099 pathogen effectors. Moreover, because the engineering can involve single amino acid variants, this
1100 approach is amenable to gene editing, making it possible when transgenesis is not an option. It
1101 remains to be determined how durable resistance gene resurrection will be considering that
1102 pathogens may evolve to counteract the introduced mutations.

1103

1104 Table 1. Summary of known NLR-suppressing effectors, their host targets, and activities.

Effector	Pathogen	Supressed NLRs	Host target	Effector activity	References
HopZ3	<i>P. syringae</i>	RPM1	RPM1	Acetylation of host RPM1 results in inactivation of immune complex.	(Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
HopBF1	<i>P. syringae</i>	RPM1	HSP90	Phosphorylation of host HSP90 results in its inactivation.	(Lopez <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
AvrPtoB	<i>P. syringae</i>	ADR1-L1, ADR1-L2	ADR1-L1, ADR1-L2	Ubiquitinates and promotes degradation of helper CC _R -NLRs, ADR1-L1 and ADR1-L2	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2023a)
XopQ	<i>X. euvesicatoria</i>	Pto, Gpa2	TFT4	Binding to host TFT4 prevents association with downstream immune-related targets.	(Saunders <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
RipAC	<i>R. solanacearum</i>	R3a, RPS2	SGT1	Association prevents phosphorylation by MAP kinases.	(Yu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Lso-HPE1	<i>C. liberibacter</i>	Prf	Unknown	Unknown.	(Levy <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
RHA1b	<i>G. pallida</i>	Prf, Rx, Rpi-blb1, Gpa2, Bs4	Unknown host E2 ubiquitin conjugation enzymes	Ubiquitination of target NLRs prevents their accumulation.	(Kud <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
SS4, SS18, SS19	<i>G. rostochiensis</i>	Rx	Unknown	Unknown.	(Ali <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
SS15	<i>G. rostochiensis</i>	All NRC2/3-dependent sensor NLRs	NRC2, NRC3	Binds NB-ARC domain to prevent activation and oligomerization.	(Ali <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Contreras <i>et al.</i> , 2023a;

					Derevnina <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
SPRYSEC34, SS10	<i>G. rostochiensis</i>	Rpi-blb2	Unknown	Unknown.	(Ali <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Derevnina <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
IPI-O4	<i>P. infestans</i>	RB (also known as Rpi-blb1)	RB	Binding to CC-domain of RB immune signalling.	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Karki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
PITG-15278	<i>P. infestans</i>	Rpi-blb2	Unknown	Unknown	(Derevnina <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Oh <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Avr1	<i>F. oxysporum f. sp. lycopersici</i>	I2 and I3	Unknown	Unknown.	(Houterman <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

1105

1106

1107 Discussion

1108

1109 In this review, we highlight some of the recent findings on NLR biology, covering how these
1110 immune receptors evolve, sense pathogens, and get activated. It is now becoming clear that our
1111 view of NLRs must move beyond single genetic and functional units to a receptor network
1112 perspective (Wu Derevnina review 2018). The study of NLRs need to also move beyond a few
1113 model plant species. Based on their RefPlantNLR database, Kourelis et al. reported that, although
1114 approximately 500 NLRs have been experimentally validated, about 80% of seed plant clades still
1115 do not have a single NLR that has been experimentally confirmed. Future studies on NLRs will
1116 require a broader, phylogenetically informed view.

1117

1118 A hallmark of NLR biology and evolution is sub-functionalization. While some singleton NLRs
1119 are individual functional units, the inter-NLR cooperation and modulation exhibited in NLR pairs
1120 and in PRR-NLR networks such as the NRC and NRG/ADR1 network reveals that over
1121 evolutionary time, immune receptor specialization has likely led to new functions or degeneration
1122 for different NLR domains. The sensor-helper specialization of networked NLRs increases their
1123 versatility and evolvability, helping the plant immune system to keep up with rapidly evolving
1124 pathogens. Moreover, the redundancy exhibited by these signaling networks makes them more
1125 robust and difficult to suppress by pathogens. As we uncover this genetic and functional NLR
1126 diversity, it is imperative to move beyond the simplified view of the NLR tripartite domain
1127 architecture and integrate the complexity of these higher order NLR signaling configurations into
1128 understanding of NLR domain function and evolution to inform future research.

1129

1130 Ever since the cloning of the first NLR genes in the 1990s, the field has been hampered by the
1131 difficulty of studying activated NLR *in planta* given that they trigger a cell death response. This has
1132 been addressed by the discovery of the N-terminal MADA a1 helix given that mutations in this
1133 motif abolish cell death activity without compromising immune receptor activation, plasma
1134 membrane association, and oligomerization. Many of the advances described in this article would
1135 not have been possible without these N-terminal mutants, due to the early onset cell death
1136 triggered by immune receptor activation. Nonetheless, even though these MADA-motif mutants
1137 are a valuable tool to study activated CC-NLRs, future studies will need to consider experiments
1138 with wild-type sequences whenever possible.

1139

1140 While the new conceptual framework provided by the elucidation of the structure and activation
1141 mechanisms of various NLR resistosomes represents a major advance for the plant NLR field,
1142 there is still much work to be done in understanding how paired and networked NLRs function,
1143 with many important questions remaining unanswered. What is the molecular basis of the
1144 evolutionary transition of NLRs from singletons to pairs and networks? How do sensors and
1145 helpers communicate and activate each other in NLR pairs and networks? How are immune
1146 receptor networks efficiently regulated? The interplay between cell-surface receptors, sensor
1147 NLRs, helper NLRs, modulator NLRs and the effectors that activate or suppress them is incredibly
1148 complex. Multi-disciplinary approaches are required to disentangle how these PRR/NLR immune
1149 receptor networks function and evolve. Answering these questions holds the potential to deepen
1150 our understanding of the plant immune system and unlock a new era of disease resistance breeding
1151 (Box 1).

1152

1153 **Box 1: In need of answers**

1154 1- How do additional domains become integrated into the canonical NLR domain structure?
1155 How do these integrated domains (IDs) evolve following integration? How do they co-
1156 evolve with their cognate effectors and with their NLR chassis? Understanding how NLR-
1157 IDs evolve and function in nature may enable bioengineering of novel made-to-order
1158 disease resistance genes.

1159 2- How do NLR pairs and networks evolve? How do they activate and how are they
1160 regulated? What are the molecular determinants for sensor-helper compatibility
1161 within NLR networks? Elucidating the molecular basis of sensor-helper specificity
1162 could inform bioengineering efforts to make the plant immune system more robust against
1163 pathogen perturbation.

1164 3- What are the precise mechanisms by which activated CC-NLR and CC_R-NLR resistosomes
1165 mediate immune signaling and disease resistance? While their calcium channel activity is
1166 required for cell death, the precise downstream mechanisms by which NLR resistosomes
1167 trigger cell death are not understood.

1168 4- What is the molecular link between cell-surface and intracellular immune receptors?
1169 Understanding the interplay synergies and dependencies of cell-surface and intracellular
1170 immunity is key to achieve a more holistic view of the plant immune system.

- 1171 5- What are the molecular determinants of sub-cellular NLR localization pre- and post-
1172 activation? What is the nature of the membrane-associated puncta formed by NLR
1173 resistosomes?
- 1174 6- To what degree do plants use NLRs to respond to pathogens in a cell type or tissue specific
1175 manner? How does NLR signaling function in different plant tissues? Are there cell-
1176 autonomous and non-cell-autonomous NLR responses?
- 1177 7- How prevalent are NLR suppressing effectors? What is their precise contribution to
1178 pathogen virulence? NLR suppressing effectors may be masking a vast and yet untapped
1179 reservoir of disease resistance genes in crop genomes. A better understanding of how
1180 pathogens suppress NLR signaling may enable new disease resistance strategies.
- 1181

1182 **Materials & Methods:**

1183

1184 **NLR identification and phylogenetic analyses for Figure 2.**

1185

1186 NLRtracker (Kourelis *et al.*, 2021) was used to extract the NLRs from the proteomes of the
1187 *Arabidopsis thaliana* (GCF_000001735.4), *Glycine max* (GCF_000004515.6), *Solanum lycopersicum*
1188 (GCF_000188115.4), *Nicotiana benthamiana* (<https://nbenthamiana.jp/>), *Lactuca sativa*
1189 (GCF_002870075.2), *Oryza sativa* (GCF_001433935.1), *Hordeum vulgare* (GCF_904849725.1),
1190 *Spinacia oleracea* (GCF_002007265.1), and *Beta vulgaris* (GCF_002917755.1), representing four
1191 major plant phyla. Only proteins with canonical NLR domain architecture and intact NB-ARC
1192 domain were kept from NLRtracker output ("CNL","NL","CNLO","CONL", "RNL",
1193 "BCNL","BCNLO","TNL","TNLO") and were deduplicated using CD-HIT (-c 1.0) (Fu *et al.*,
1194 2012). The NB-ARC domains for the remaining sequences were extracted from NLRtracker
1195 output and aligned with RefPlantNLR (Kourelis *et al.*, 2021) using MAFFT v7.490 (Kato &
1196 Standley, 2013). The alignment was then used to construct an approximately-maximum-likelihood
1197 phylogenetic tree using FastTree v2.1.11 (default options) (Price *et al.*, 2009). The tree was
1198 visualized using iTOL (Letunic & Bork, 2021) and annotated manually. The species tree was
1199 obtained from NCBI common taxonomy tree
1200 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/CommonTree/wwwcmt.cgi>). The NRC clade tree
1201 was constructed using the same methods with the extracted sequences from highlighted tree
1202 region. Metadata and sequences used are available in the **Supplementary Data**.

1203

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1226

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